

Inspiration for Action

Davos Congress Centre
26 June - 1 July 2022

World Biodiversity Forum – Final Resolution

Davos, Switzerland June 29, 2022

Adopted by acclamation by the participants of the second World Biodiversity Forum.

Distributed to participants and interested parties for redistribution.

The World Biodiversity Forum 2022 (<https://www.worldbiodiversityforum.org/>) was organised by bioDISCOVERY (<https://biodiscovery.earth/>), a Global Research Network (GRN) of FutureEarth (<https://futureearth.org/>), fostering collaborative interdisciplinary activities on biodiversity and ecosystem science, and the University of Zurich (<https://www.uzh.ch/>) and its Research Priority Programme on “Global Change and Biodiversity” (<https://www.gcb.uzh.ch/>).

The World Biodiversity Forum, held from 26 June to 1 July 2022 in Davos, Switzerland.

Confirming that the Forum’s mission is to advance biodiversity research in an integrative, interdisciplinary, and transparent fashion, and advance transdisciplinary approaches in biodiversity,

Confirming that the Forum’s aim is to support and accelerate transformative approaches ranging from fundamental research to implementation,

Recognizing that the Forum’s mission is to facilitate interactions between all stakeholders relevant to biodiversity, including private, corporate, governmental, non-governmental, non-profit, academic, educators and other parties acting within and across national and international borders,

Recognizing that the Forum is developing into a global centre servicing the advancement of biodiversity competencies with all involved parties,

Considering that it is essential that the Forum continues to be effectively and interactively supported by key stakeholders, philanthropies, industries and international organisations,

Congratulates the Forum organisers on its contributions to advancing integrative and interdisciplinary biodiversity research and its implementation, and *considering* the unique, broad, and interdisciplinary work accomplished by the Forum,

Urges involved parties both to maintain and enhance their support for the Forum and *encourages* parties who are not yet involved to join the Forum.

Urges governments to address all drivers of biodiversity loss and ecosystem degradation and to consider possibilities to steer away from economic paradigms causing biodiversity loss and social injustice to systems that restore power balances and are mutually beneficial for both humanity and the ecosystems it lives in, and

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Makes the following recommendations:

1. Concerned about the urgency of addressing the triple planetary crisis¹, we underline the need for a holistic governance approach to reverse biodiversity loss and recommend to:
 - Urge public, institutional and private actors to act against biodiversity loss, to move towards transformative change, and to assess biodiversity footprints of their activities in order to understand how these activities drive biodiversity loss and mitigate the latter by adapting their practices.
 - Take into account negative externalities on biodiversity at the global and national levels when taking decisive actions for global change (climate, overexploitation, pollution, invasive species and land use).
 - Define biodiversity protection comprehensively to coexist with nature, including the protection of the rights of indigenous and local communities.
 - Support guidelines on jointly addressing biodiversity and climate change in a coordinated manner to steer financial investments and generate data underlying ESG² ratings towards sustainable practices.

2. As the scientific community, we identify the need for informed research, action, and policies through a set of comprehensive biodiversity data governance principles and certification schemes and urge to:
 - Support robust, accessible, and universal biodiversity monitoring observatories and platforms that are based on common standards and data collection protocols across different knowledge systems to complement and allow calibration of existing biodiversity records databases, as well as current and future monitoring tools (e.g. through Earth Observation practices, eDNA). It shall cover a wide range of taxa across the tree of life spanning scales, biomes; assess intraspecific diversity, species' abundance, distribution and movement in a representative range of natural and anthropogenic habitats across the globe; and support the modelling of essential biodiversity variables from genes to ecosystems, facilitating future predictions of biodiversity change and the assessment of policy impacts and progress towards global biodiversity targets.
 - Follow the FAIR and CARE Principles³ in biodiversity data collection, processing, management and handling, preservation, and provision to increase the Findability, Accessibility, Reusability, and scientific accuracy of the data and research based on it while also guaranteeing Collective Benefits, Authority to control, Responsibility as well as Ethics. Following these principles will increase scientific quality, and efficiency, as well as trust on behalf of the general public and local and Indigenous peoples.

¹ Biodiversity, climate and pollution.

² Environmental, Social, and Governance.

³ The FAIR and CARE Principles are sets of principles, which provide guidance to make data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable while also following data governance principles essential for Indigenous and Local Knowledge such as Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility and Ethics.

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- Foster business activities steered towards the mitigation of biodiversity loss by defining a universal, certified, and monitored measurement system leading towards a nature-positive economy, and welcome initiatives such as the one being prepared by the Task Force on Nature-Related Financial Disclosures (TNFD).
3. Knowing about the practical importance of education, capacity-building and awareness-raising to conserve biodiversity, we strongly suggest to:
- Raise awareness on the importance of biodiversity to our everyday life through strengthened public education campaigns in order to equally inform decision-makers and the public to take action on biodiversity conservation and restoration.
 - Promote the knowledge and value of healthy and diverse ecosystems in primary and secondary schools, beginning with communities, considering local context and cultural diversity and extending to planetary scale.
4. Being aware of the different needs of specific ecosystems when taking conservation action, we advise to:
- Recognize, in the context of the 2022 International Year of Sustainable Mountain Development, that conservation and promotion of mountain biodiversity, as a rapidly changing environmental common, is central to sustainable development and relying on cross-scale and co-produced social-ecological data and knowledge.
 - Foster sustainable soil management, which encourages landscape heterogeneity through incentivized biodiversity-friendly agricultural practices and educational programs about the critical value of soil biodiversity.
 - Mainstream biodiversity considerations into tree planting programs for carbon sequestration, including in urban areas, and other restoration programs globally, using local expertise and existing tools to guide species selection, and to deliver joint and equitable benefits for people and broader biodiversity.
 - Recognize the value of low-diversity ecosystems with evolutionary distinct cold-adapted species at the three poles of the Earth, the Arctic, Antarctic and high altitude systems.
 - Contribute “science we need for the ocean we want” to achieve the vision of the United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021-2023)
 - Reconstruct space-time composition of most endangered ecosystems by initiating whole DNA sequenced open accessible species databases with unique location identifiers.

In agreement with the recent global trend recognising biodiversity loss as one of the main global planetary risks (WEF, UNFCCC, G7, IPBES, UNCBD) we urge national governments and international organisations to act responsibly and without delay towards reverting biodiversity loss by including all relevant stakeholders with the ultimate goal to safeguard all life on Earth.⁴

⁴ This Resolution is the result of a co-creation process led by bioDISCOVERY and the URPP Global Change and Biodiversity and the University of Zurich using the policy crowdsourcing methodology and platform Policy Kitchen, developed by the think tank foraus. The co-creation took place online during multiple weeks ahead of the World Biodiversity Forum (WBF) as well as during the latter. The Resolution was presented at the Conference Dinner on 29.06.2022. We would like to express our gratitude to all the WBF participants who actively contributed to this process.